

COMPLEX CATALOGUE OF HIGH SPEED SOLAR STREAMS IN THE SOLAR WIND

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The continuous development of technological system both on Earth and on board its missions within its atmosphere makes solar weather one of the most important current issues. Consequently, the study of space weather impact on Earth and its environment is a crucial part of science.

Space weather is driven by the solar wind. Any change in its composition and variability could impact the magnetosphere. High speed solar streams in the solar wind are travelling through the heliosphere towards the Earth's orbit and beyond, inducing a lot of interplanetary disturbances that could cause geomagnetic storms (GSs), polar auroras and even the geomagnetically induced currents (GIC) in the large extent terrestrial technological systems.

Complex databases with precompiled data for describing various phenomena in the solar wind are, therefore, very useful for the scientific community.

This work will describe the structure of the catalogue that is available at <http://www.geodin.ro/varsiti/>. This catalogue (Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the webpage) is organised in two different sections. The first one is a description of the basic measurements for the high speed streams, start time, the initial ($V0$) and maximum velocity in the second day of the stream ($V1$), DtI – time interval between $V0$ and $V1$ (in number of 3-hr intervals), the maximum velocity ($Vmax$), d – the duration (days), the gradients of the plasma speed: $\Delta V1 = V1-V0$ and $\Delta VM = Vmax-V0$, the intensity of the stream defined as $I = \Delta Vmax \times d$ and their solar CH (Coronal Holes) sources. The main interplanetary magnetic field polarity during streams is also mentioned.

No	Year	Month	Day	V0 (km/s)	V1 (km/s)	DtI	Vmax (km/s)	d	I	Source	Bz (mT)	Dt_date (min)	Bz_min (mT)	Bz_max (mT)	SSC (state)	Energy extraction (E23)	Energy extraction (E27)	SYM_min	SYM_max					
1	2014	1	5	4	361	308	7	606	5.6	215.7	215.7	1201.06	CHP06	+										
2	2014	1	31	2	409.3	509	6	604	4.1	159.7	184.7	792.97	CHP09	+										
3	2014	1	26	6	343.3	359.7	10	554	6	176.4	211.7	1270.2	CHP	-	-39	-01:20:16	-4	-01:20:14	201:38:22	2.04E+17	1.24E+18	-65	-01:20:16:42	
4	2014	2	2	1	270	396.3	15	277	9	126.3	207	1461	CHP13	nc	-52	-02:03:02	-4.3	-02:03:01	8:55E+14	5:58E+16	-60	-02:03:02:52		
5	2014	2	18	2	375	553.3	13	142.2	8	249.3	267.3	1606.2	CHP15	-	-37	-02:16:10	-3.1	-02:16:10	6:26E+15	1:38E+17	-58	-02:16:10:44		
6	2014	2	26	7	303.3	418	8	418	6.2	114.7	114.7	481.14	CHP16	+	-33	-02:19:08	-2.3	-02:19:04			-33	-02:19:05:26		
7	2014	3	11	1	193	289.7	14	140.7	4	157.7	157.7	633.8	CHP18	+										
8	2014	3	15	1	345	289.7	15	140.7	5.1	152.7	214.7	1217.17	CHP18	-	-38	-03:06:21	-12.7	-03:06:19			1.42E+16	2:39E+17	-110	-03:06:21:25
9	2014	3	11	2	269	556	6	556	3.5	146	146	461	CHP20	+										
10	2014	3	14	6	373	398.2	2	870.2	6	165.3	167.3	1183.8	CHP21	-	-36	-03:15:07	-4.2	-03:15:06	08:14:21	1.07E+17	8:80E+17	-62	-03:15:07:16	
11	2014	3	23	1	303.7	303	15	148.7	3.2	129.3	133	489	CHP23	+										
12	2014	3	27	2	367	502	14	136.7	5.4	129	164.3	633.30	CHP24	+	-38	-03:16:23	-5.3	-03:16:23	3.41E+16	3:17E+16	-69	-03:16:23:41		
13	2014	4	2	3	324.3	293.3	5	493.2	8.9	167	167	1466.3	CHP26	++	-36	-04:02:25	-6.4	-04:02:25	2:24E+16	2:34E+17	-65	-04:02:25:47		
14	2014	4	31	2	340.7	273.3	14	609.2	8.4	132.6	268.6	2296.04	CHP27	+	-36	-04:15:05	-7.9	-04:15:03	4:20E+16	4:88E+17	-69	-04:15:04:44		
15	2014	4	21	1	373.3	363.3	14	142.2	8.5	156	205	1742.5	CHP29	+	-39	-04:14:20	-5.4	-04:14:18	04:14:37	1:04E+17	1:17E+17	-69	-04:14:20:26	
16	2014	4	30	2	347	485	14	471.2	8.1	156	204.3	1366.93	CHP30	+	-33	-05:02:03	-5.1	-05:02:01			-54	-05:02:03:16		
17	2014	5	6	3	373.3	517.7	6	667.7	6.9	142.4	262.4	2017.56	CHP	-	-40	-05:08:08	-11.2	-05:08:05	1.06E+16	2:28E+17	-105	-05:08:08:15		
18	2014	5	14	4	361.3	327.7	12	474.2	7.4	152.2	214.2	1214.2	CHP	-	-41	-05:09:21	-4.8	-05:09:18			-61	-05:09:21:36		

Fig. 1 Screenshot of the Catalogue's webpage

The second part of the catalogue lists parameters related to the geomagnetic storms that were associated with the detected high speed stream. The criteria for selecting the associated storm was that the storm would begin after the onset of the stream, following the definition of the geomagnetic storm using the Disturbance Storm Time (Dst) index. This part lists the moment of the minimum for the Dst index given by the calendar date format: month, day and hour (mm:dd:hh), a description of its commencement (storm with sudden commencement - SSC). The minimum negative values of the southern component of the heliospheric magnetic field (B_z , in nT) registered just before the minimum Dst values and its time (mm:dd:hh) is also included. In order to give a better estimate of the GS evolution and characteristics, our catalogue also includes estimated values for the energy deposited in the magnetosphere from solar wind (for GSs with $Dst \leq -50$ nT), computed using the Akasofu parameter (Akasofu, 1981), ϵ , integrated over the main phase of the geomagnetic storms and an improved version of this formula given by Wang et al. (2014), W. Generally, one single GS is induced by a HSS. However, there are some cases when, during a complex HSS, two or even more (minor) GSs are registered; in such cases, the parameters of the successive geomagnetic storms will appear on successive rows in the catalogue.

Fig. 2 Solar Wind Speed and Density Plots for April 2018

A detailed analysis of a high speed stream from April 2018 with a geomagnetic storm associated will be described in detail.

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References

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